

The Influence of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Performance Mediated by Work Discipline of Employees of the One Stop Integrated Service and Investment Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze the significant influence of motivation, organizational culture on work discipline, significant influence of motivation and organizational culture on employee performance, significant influence of work discipline on employee performance, analyze work discipline mediate work motivation on performance and analyze work discipline mediate culture organization on the performance of employees of the Investment Service and One Stop Integrated Service in Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province. In this study, data analysis and hypothesis testing were carried out using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) analysis with the SmartPLS 3.0 application. The results of the study show that there is an influence of organizational culture and motivation on employee work discipline, there is no influence of motivation and organizational culture on performance, there is an influence of work discipline on performance, work discipline does not mediate the influence of motivation on employee performance of the Regency Investment and One-Stop Service Office. Tapin.

KEYWORDS: Discipline, Motivation, Organizational Culture, Performance

INTRODUCTION

The most important resource for an institution or organization is human resources, namely people who have provided their energy, talent, creativity and effort to the organization (Handoko, 2014: 35). Simamora (2014:24) states that performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective authority and responsibilities, in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals. as well as ethics. According to Mathis and Jackson (2011: 28) performance is assessed by the quantity of work that can be done by someone in one working day, quality in compliance with procedures and discipline, reliability in carrying out the work required with minimum supervision, attendance at work every day and in accordance with working hours, and the ability to collaborate with other people in completing assigned tasks and work so as to achieve maximum efficiency. Research by Rusda and Silalahi (2015), Prawatya and Raharjo (2012), Ray (2015) states that variables that influence employee performance which are the result of a person's work function/activities in an organization to achieve organizational goals within a certain time period consist of work discipline and organizational culture. Meanwhile, research by Liana and Irawati (2014) states that work motivation is a variable that mediates the relationship between work discipline and performance. Meanwhile, research by Nikpour (2017) states that organizational commitment is a mediating variable between organizational culture and employee performance. From these various studies, researchers tried to test the influence of work motivation and organizational culture on performance with discipline as a mediating variable.

A common phenomenon regarding work motivation at the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service is a lack of sense of responsibility from employees towards their work, such as work not being completed on time, which can be done quickly, but is often slowed down. Apart from that, employees often have a relaxed and irresponsible attitude in dealing with work situations in the workplace. Motivation is a condition or energy that moves oneself/employees to achieve the goals of the organization and the employees themselves. Apart from that, motivation is a factor that encourages a person to carry out a certain activity, therefore motivation is often interpreted as a factor that drives a person's behavior. Every activity carried out by a person must have factors that encourage the activity, a person's needs and desires are different, this happens because of the mental processes that have occurred within a person. Leaders need to develop effective motivation techniques that can be used to motivate their subordinates. A leader

must be able to control his subordinates and provide good motivation. Lack of motivation from superiors can affect employee performance, apart from the employee's own motivational factors.

Organizational culture at the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service is related to how employees understand the cultural characteristics of an organization and is not related to whether employees like those characteristics or not. Organizational culture represents a shared perception of organizational members or in other words, culture is a system of shared meaning. Therefore, the hope that is built from this is that individuals who have different backgrounds or are at different levels in the organization will understand organizational culture in a similar sense. Organizational culture is also very important in improving employee performance.

Performance is a work result achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skill, experience, seriousness and time. Increasing employee work in an organization is very necessary so that the goals desired by the organization can be realized well. The performance of an organization will increase if there is cooperation and good relationships between leaders and employees. By improving employee performance, organizational performance will improve. For this reason, employees should be treated as work partners and not just workers.

Work discipline is an attitude of respecting, appreciating and obeying rules and regulations. Discipline is one of the things that must be maintained and continuously improved so that employees become accustomed to working according to the rules. A person who arrives on time, carries out tasks according to the work schedule that has been set, follows every rule and standard, the results of his work will be of higher quality because the work carried out is right on target and objective. This can be clearly seen by achieving targets that have been programmed, the amount of responsibility for carrying out tasks, the high level of work enthusiasm and enthusiasm and employee initiative in carrying out work. Furthermore, such working conditions will encourage employees to produce quality work which will later be profitable for the employees themselves. Previous research states that work discipline has a positive influence on employee work results. Employees who are disciplined in working according to company rules will usually have good performance. (Prawatya and Raharjo (2012:31).

A special phenomenon that occurs in the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service is a tendency for employee performance to decline, even though the community expects the government to ensure that employee performance meets expectations. The organization has the duty to provide encouragement to employees, so that they work diligently. so as to achieve organizational targets. From observations made by researchers, it was found that several weaknesses were still shown by employees, namely that they were less motivated by their work, which made them not become disciplined individuals. There are those who do not arrive on time when entering the office, delay office tasks, lack discipline, cannot make good use of office facilities and there are still some employees who leave their duties during working hours without explanation. Based on existing problems, the questions in this research are:

1. Does work motivation have a significant effect on the work discipline of employees of the Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province?
2. Does organizational culture have a significant effect on the work discipline of employees of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province?
3. Does work motivation have a significant effect on the performance of employees of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province?
4. Does organizational culture have a significant effect on the performance of employees of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province?
5. Does work discipline have a significant effect on the performance of employees of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province?
6. Does work discipline mediate work motivation on the performance of employees of the Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province?
7. Does work discipline mediate organizational culture on the performance of employees of the Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province?

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. *Work motivation*

Motivation is basically an unsatisfied internal need that creates tensions that stimulate drives from within the individual. According to Robbins (2016: 166), motivation itself is defined as the willingness to expend a high level of effort for organizational goals, which is conditioned by the ability of that effort to fulfill an individual need. Motivation is also defined as a drive from within an individual based on which to behave in a certain way to fulfill. BA Setiono, (2017:39), suggests that motivation is a process where needs encourage a person to carry out a series of activities that lead to achieving certain goals. If needs have been met then satisfaction will be achieved. A group of unsatisfied needs will cause tension, so it is necessary to carry out a series of activities to seek the achievement of specific goals that can satisfy this group of needs, so that tension is reduced. Pinder, (2013:45) believes that work motivation is a set of forces both originating from within oneself and from outside a person that encourages one to start working behavior, according to a certain format, direction, intensity and time period.

Usmara (2016:14) motivation is a collection of forces that come from within and outside the individual which initiates attitudes and determines the form of direction and intensity. Luthans (2015: 57) suggests that motivation is a psychological process through which unsatisfied desires are directed towards achieving goals/incentives. This definition shows that motivation describes a force that moves people to behave in a certain way. According to Stokes (2016:92) work motivation is an incentive for someone to do their job better, work motivation is also a factor that makes the difference between success and failure in many things and is emotional energy which is very important for a new job.

Stoner (2015:260) defines performance as the quantity and quality of work completed by individuals. Performance includes the following dimensions: work quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, independence, commitment. From the definition above, work motivation is a drive from within that gives rise to various needs and attitudes of employees in facing work situations in the company, which is a condition or energy that moves employees so that they work mentally prepared, physically healthy, understand the situation and conditions and try hard to achieve work targets (the main goals of the organization) that are directed and aimed at achieving the company's organizational goals.

Indicators of Work Motivation According to Hamzah B. Uno (2013: 73) dimensions and indicators of work motivation can be grouped as follows:

- a. Internal motivation includes: Responsibility in carrying out tasks, carrying out tasks with clear targets, having clear and challenging goals, providing feedback on the results of work, having a sense of enjoyment in working, always trying to outperform others and prioritizing the achievements of what one does
- b. External motivation includes: Always trying to meet life's needs and work needs, Happy to get praise for what he does, Working with the desire to get incentives, Working with the hope of getting attention from friends and superiors.

b. *Organizational culture*

Organizational culture in terms of social and political science is all the characteristics that indicate the personality of an organization: shared beliefs, values and behaviors shared by all members of the organization. Organizational culture is a tradition that is very difficult to change. BA Setiono (2017) argues that "Organizational culture refers to a system of shared meaning held by members that differentiates the organization from other organizations. This system, when examined more closely, constitutes a set of key characteristics valued by the organization. Suwanto and Koesharto (2015:82) state that: "In general, a company or organization consists of a number of people with diverse backgrounds, personalities, emotions and egos.

Organizational culture will increase employee work motivation by giving them a feeling of belonging, loyalty, trust, values and encouraging them to think positively about themselves and the organization. In this way, the organization maximizes employee potential and wins the competition. Organizational culture will also ultimately function as a motivator for employees in carrying out their work. Culture has been an important concept in understanding human societies and groups for a long time. Culture in the anthropological and historical sense is the essence of different groups and societies regarding the perspective of their members who interact with outsiders and how they accomplish what they do (Rivai, 2013: 47).

According to Pacanowsky (2015:56), culture is a way of life in an organization. Included in organizational culture is the emotional and psychological climate/atmosphere which includes the morals, attitudes and level of productivity of the members of the

organization concerned. Organizational culture also includes all existing symbols (actions, routines, conversations, etc.). The meaning and understanding of organizational culture is achieved through interaction between leaders (management) and employees. Organizational culture is a parable (metaphor) of a spider that makes a nest in the form of a web with a complicated design/shape and each web made is not the same as the other. According to Sobirin (2015:36) organizational culture can contribute to the success of company performance. Apart from that, organizational culture also functions to integrate the internal environment and adapt to the external environment. Indicators of Organizational Culture according to Wibowo (2016:54) indicators of organizational culture are as follows: 1) Innovation and courage to take risks, 2) Attention to details, 3) Orientation to work results, 4) Orientation to organizational members, 5) Orientation team, 6) Aggressiveness

c. Work Discipline

Work discipline is an employee's attitude of obedience and loyalty to all written or unwritten regulations which are reflected in the form of employee behavior and actions to achieve goals in the organization Hasibuan (2016: 193). With dimensions, namely: coming to and leaving work on time, doing work well and complying with office regulations. The indicators are as follows: 1) Utilization of office facilities, 2) Timely completion of work, 3) Accuracy in work 4) Wearing the specified uniform.

According to Ardana (2012: 134), work discipline in terms of business administration is defined as an attitude of respect, respect, obedience and obedience to applicable regulations, both written and unwritten, as well as being able to carry them out and not evade accepting the sanctions. Meanwhile, according to Rivai (2013: 825) work discipline is a tool that managers use to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change behavior and as an effort to increase a person's awareness and willingness to comply with all company regulations and applicable social norms.

Good work discipline reflects a person's sense of responsibility for the tasks assigned to him. This encourages those who voluntarily obey all regulations and are aware of their duties and responsibilities. So someone will obey/carry out all their duties with passion, work enthusiasm and the realization of the goals of the organization, employees and society. Therefore, every manager always tries to ensure that his subordinates have good discipline. A manager is said to be effective in his leadership if his subordinates are well disciplined. Discipline can be interpreted as when employees always come and go home on time, do all their work well, comply with all company regulations and applicable social norms (Fathoni, 2016: 126).

Hasibuan (2016: 193), provides a definition of discipline as awareness of one's behavior properly, not due to coercion and sadness. A person obeys organizational regulations and applicable social norms. According to Hasibuan (2016: 194), there are 8 indicators of work discipline, including: 1) Goals and abilities, 2) Leadership example, 3) Remuneration, 4) Justice, 5) Close supervision, 6) Punishment sanctions, 7) Firmness, 8) Human relations.

d. Performance

Performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. According to Bastian (2015:329) performance is a description of the level of achievement of tasks in an organization in an effort to realize the organization's goals, objectives, mission and vision. BA Setiono (2021) performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Employees are people who do work and receive compensation for their services in the form of salaries and allowances from the government. These employees carry out all work or government administration activities. So the definition of employee performance is the result of individual work in an organization. Organizational performance is the totality of work results achieved by an organization. Employee performance and organizational performance are very closely related to achieving organizational goals. Employee performance cannot be separated from the resources owned by the organization. Resources that are mobilized or carried out by employees who play an active role as actors in efforts to achieve the organization's goals.

Government Regulation (PP) Number 30 of 2019 concerning Performance Assessment of Civil Servants confirms that the SKP that has been prepared and agreed as intended is signed by the Civil Servant and determined by the Civil Servant Performance Appraisal Officer, determined every year in January. Furthermore, the SKP assessment is carried out using the results of performance measurements carried out by the Civil Servant Performance Appraisal Officer. Specifically for functional officials, the SKP assessment can take into account the assessment of the Functional Position Credit Score Assessment Team. Article 36 of

Government Regulation (PP) Number 30 of 2019 concerning Performance Assessment of Civil Servants reads: "The assessment of SKP for civil servants who experience rotation, transfer and/or other assignments related to the duties and functions of the position during the current year is carried out using the method proportionally based on the SKP period in the units where the civil servant works in the current year," for the assessment of Work Behavior, it is carried out by comparing the standards of Work Behavior in the position as intended by the Assessment of Work Behavior in the position carried out by the Civil Servant Performance Appraisal Officer and can be based on the assessment of colleagues level and/or direct subordinates.

Performance indicators according to (PP Number 30 of 2019) are as follows: 1) Specific, namely the special or typical nature of something or someone. 2) Measurable, namely in terms of determining that there is certainty in an activity which will later produce the right goals. 3) Realistic, namely something that looks real and reliable. 4) Having a time limit for achievement, that is, there is a time limit for achieving an organizational goal or target. 5) Adjusting the internal and external conditions of the organization, namely looking at existing conditions both within the organization and outside the organization.

e. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework for the relationship between work motivation, organizational culture and work discipline on the performance of employees of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province. Work motivation, organizational culture and work discipline are independent variables X1 (work motivation),

f. Hypothesis

- H1: There is a significant influence of work motivation on work discipline of employees of the Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province.
- H2: There is a significant influence of organizational culture on the work discipline of employees of the One Stop Investment and Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province
- H3: There is a significant influence of work motivation on the performance of employees of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province.
- H4: There is a significant influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of the One Stop Integrated Service and Investment Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province
- H5: There is a significant influence of work discipline on the performance of employees of the One Stop Integrated Services and Investment Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province
- H6: Work discipline does not mediate the influence of motivation on the performance of employees of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province.
- H7: Work discipline does not mediate the influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of the One Stop Integrated Service and Investment Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a cross sectional study. Which is carried out at a certain time with one focus with the aim of exploration, description and explanation. This research aims to find the existing relationship between variables, namely the relationship between work

motivation, organizational culture and work discipline with performance, then the existing relationship is proven through hypothesis testing. The sources used in this research are primary data and secondary data. The population in this study were all 70 civil servants at the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province. With details of the Head of Service: 1 person, Secretariat 20 people, Planning, Climate Development and Investment Promotion Sector 13 people, Information and Control of Investment Implementation Sector 13 people, Licensing and Non-Licensing Service Delivery Sector 13 people and Complaints, Policy and Service Reporting Sector 10 person. The sample in this study were all civil servants of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province, totaling 70 people. Data collection techniques use questionnaires, observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis techniques use Validity Test, Reliability Test, then the data is analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the Smart PLS 3.0 application

RESULT

The first model design carried out with SmartPLS can be seen in Figure 1 below.:

Figure 1: Outer Model Design

Convergent Validity

To measure indicator validity, it can be seen from the SmartPLS output, namely outer loadings. An indicator is declared valid if it has an outer loadings value above 0.5 (outer loadings value > 0.5)]. The first outer loadings measurement can be seen in Table 5.11.

Table 1. First Outer Loadings Measurement

Indicator	Outer Loadings Value	Critical Value	Information
X1.1	0,748	0,5	Valid
X1.2	0,907	0,5	Valid
X1.3	0,897	0,5	Valid
X1.4	0,862	0,5	Valid
X1.5	0,725	0,5	Valid

X1.6	0,800	0,5	Valid
X1.7	0,771	0,5	Valid
X1.8	0,804	0,5	Valid
X1.9	0,653	0,5	Valid
X1.10	0,827	0,5	Valid
X1.11	0,709	0,5	Valid
X1.12	0,811	0,5	Valid
X1.13	0,678	0,5	Valid
X1.14	0,765	0,5	Valid
X1.15	0,679	0,5	Valid
X1.16	0,798	0,5	Valid
X1.17	0,897	0,5	Valid
X1.18	0,891	0,5	Valid
X1.19	0,777	0,5	Valid
X1.20	0,678	0,5	Valid
X2.1	0,746	0,5	Valid
X2.2	0,904	0,5	Valid
X2.3	0,898	0,5	Valid
X2.4	0,863	0,5	Valid
X2.5	0,726	0,5	Valid
X2.6	0,792	0,5	Valid
X2.7	0,772	0,5	Valid
X2.8	0,807	0,5	Valid
X2.9	0,319	0,5	Invalid
X2.10	0,655	0,5	Valid
X2.11	0,824	0,5	Valid
Z.1	0,327	0,5	Invalid
Z.2	0,859	0,5	Valid
Z.3	0,746	0,5	Valid
Z.4	0,851	0,5	Valid
Z.5	0,800	0,5	Valid
Z.6	0,805	0,5	Valid
Z.7	0,661	0,5	Valid
Z.8	0,669	0,5	Valid
Z.9	0,789	0,5	Valid
Z.10	0,678	0,5	Valid
Y.1	0,118	0,5	Invalid
Y.2	-0,175	0,5	Invalid
Y.3	0,769	0,5	Valid
Y.4	0,874	0,5	Valid
Y.5	0,801	0,5	Valid
Y.6	0,797	0,5	Valid

Source: Data processed

Based on Table 1, by measuring the outer loadings value, there are 4 indicators that do not meet the critical value and are therefore declared invalid. These indicators are X2.9, Z1, Y1, and Y2. So, for further measurements these indicators are removed. The following is a diagram of the outer loadings of each indicator in the research model which is the second model.

Figure 2: Second Model Estimates

After the invalid indicators in the first outer loadings measurement are removed, the second outer loadings measurement is then carried out again. The second outer loadings value can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Second Outer Loadings Measurement

Indicator	Outer Loadings Value	Critical Value	Information
X1.1	0,748	0,5	Valid
X1.2	0,907	0,5	Valid
X1.3	0,897	0,5	Valid
X1.4	0,862	0,5	Valid
X1.5	0,725	0,5	Valid
X1.6	0,800	0,5	Valid
X1.7	0,771	0,5	Valid
X1.8	0,804	0,5	Valid

X1.9	0,653	0,5	Valid
X1.10	0,827	0,5	Valid
X1.11	0,709	0,5	Valid
X1.12	0,811	0,5	Valid
X1.13	0,678	0,5	Valid
X1.14	0,765	0,5	Valid
X1.15	0,679	0,5	Valid
X1.16	0,798	0,5	Valid
X1.17	0,897	0,5	Valid
X1.18	0,891	0,5	Valid
X11.9	0,777	0,5	Valid
X1.20	0,678	0,5	Valid
X2.1	0,746	0,5	Valid
X2.2	0,904	0,5	Valid
X2.3	0,898	0,5	Valid
X2.4	0,863	0,5	Valid
X2.5	0,726	0,5	Valid
X2.6	0,792	0,5	Valid
X2.7	0,772	0,5	Valid
X2.8	0,807	0,5	Valid
X2.10	0,655	0,5	Valid
X2.11	0,824	0,5	Valid
Z.2	0,859	0,5	Valid
Z.3	0,746	0,5	Valid
Z.4	0,851	0,5	Valid
Z.5	0,800	0,5	Valid
Z.6	0,805	0,5	Valid
Z.7	0,661	0,5	Valid
Z.8	0,669	0,5	Valid
Z.9	0,789	0,5	Valid
Z.10	0,678	0,5	Valid
Y.3	0,769	0,5	Valid
Y.4	0,874	0,5	Valid
Y.5	0,801	0,5	Valid
Y.6	0,797	0,5	Valid

Source: Data processed

Based on Table 2, it is found that all indicators have met the critical values, so that all indicators in the second model can be declared valid.

Discriminant Validity

Validity can also be seen from convergent validity by looking at the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) output on SmartPLS. An indicator is declared valid if it has an AVE value above 0.5. The AVE value in the outer model evaluation using SmartPLS can be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Value

Construct	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
X1	0.645
X2	0.594
Y	0.620
Z	0.627

Source: Data processed

Table 3 shows that all constructs in the research model have an AVE value above 0.5, which means that all indicators in the construct are said to be valid. The lowest AVE value is 0.667 in the Z construct.

Composite Reliability

The composite reliability value of the indicator block that measures the construct can be used as a rule as to whether the indicator is reliable or not. To be able to say that an indicator is reliable, the composite reliability value must be above 0.7. Composite reliability is a closer approximation with the assumption that the parameter estimates are accurate. The results of indicator reliability tests that measure constructs with composite reliability values can be seen from the SmartPLS output in Table 4.

Table 4. Composite Reliability Values

Construct	Composite Reliability
X1	0,947
X2	0,939
Y	0,89
Z	0,909

Source: Data processed

The table above shows that the composite reliability value for all constructs is above 0.7. So that the constructs that make up the estimation model are reliable.

Cronbachs alpha

Reliability measurements can also be seen by the Cronbach's alpha value from the SmartPLS output results. A construct is said to be reliable if it has a Cronbach's alpha value above 0.6. Cronbach's alpha values can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Cronbach Alpha Value

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha
X1	0,937
X2	0,926
Y	0,844
Z	0,879

Source: Data processed

It can be seen in Table 5 that all constructs have met the reliable criteria, because they have a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.6.

Inner Model

Table 6. R-Square Value

Construct	R-Square
Y	0,982
Z	0,951

Source: Data processed

Judging from the R-square output by SmartPLS, the interpretation is that the endogenous construct Y in the estimated model is 0.982. This means that constructs X1, X2 and Z can explain 98% of construct Y and are included in the good inner model category. For the endogenous construct Z in the estimated model it is obtained at 0.951. This means that constructs X1 and X2 can explain 30.8% of the KPD construct which falls into the weak inner model category. For the endogenous construct Z, the estimated model is 95%. Judging from the R-square output results from the dependent variable Z, it indicates that the inner model (structural model) in this study is included in the good category. Next is to calculate the Q-square model. Q-square can be seen in the blindfolding calculation results in the construct cross validated redundancy section. The results of these calculations can be seen in the following table

Table 7. Construct Cross Validated Redundancy

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q2
X1	700,000	700,000	
X2	770,000	770,000	
Y	490,000	299,666	0,388
Z	490,000	254,156	0,481

Source: Data processed

From the calculation results in the table above. Q2 value is 0.388. Because the Q2 value is more than zero, the model has fulfilled predictive relevance where the model has been reconstructed well. Once the value of Q2 is known, the value of the q-square effect size can be calculated. The q2 calculation formula is Q2 included minus Q2 excluded compared to 1 – Q2 included. Q2 predictive relevance included is the Q2 value at which all variables enter the model. The value of Q2 predictive relevance included can be known from the Q2 dependent variable, in this study the purchase intention variable. Q2 predictive relevance excluded is the Q2 value of the dependent variable (purchase intention) when the variable whose effect size you want to know is removed from the model. The results of the q2 calculation can be seen in the following table.

Table 8. Q2 Effect Size

Variable	Q2 Predictive relevance included	Q2 Predictive relevance excluded	q2	Category
X1	0,388	0,39	-0,00326797	Lemah Negatif
X2		0,389	-0,00163399	Lemah Negatif
Z		0,373	0,0245098	lemah

Source: Data processed

Pengkategorian nilai Q2 adalah 0,02 (lemah), 0,15 (sedang/moderat), dan 0,35 (besar). Dari tabel 8 diketahui bahwa dampak relatif model struktural terhadap pengukuran variabel dependen cukup lemah. Variabel prediktor tidak menunjukkan perubahan pengaruh yang signifikan baik ketika variabel tersebut ada dalam model maupun dikeluarkan dari model. Nilai R2 included merupakan nilai R2 variabel dependen ketika semua variabel masuk ke dalam model. Nilai ini terdapat pada variabel endogen terakhir dari model yaitu variabel kinerja pegawai. Nilai atau skor R-square included tersebut lalu dibandingkan dengan nilai R-square excluded untuk mencari nilai f-square effect size (f2). Nilai R2 excluded merupakan nilai R2 variabel laten endogen (kerja pegawai) ketika variabel yang ingin diketahui effect size-nya dikeluarkan dari model. Nilai R2 included maupun excluded serta hasil perhitungan f2 disajikan dalam tabel. berikut.

Table 9. F2 Effect Size

Variable	R2 Include	R2 Exclude	f2	Category
X1	0,982	0,976	0,33333333	Moderat
X2		0,976	0,33333333	Moderat
Z		0,925	3,16666667	Kuat

Source: Data processed

Just like the division of categories in q2, the f2 category is also divided into three, namely 0.02 is a weak influence, 0.15 is a medium influence, and 0.35 is a strong influence. From table 9 it is known that all work motivation variables (X1) and organizational culture (X2) have a moderate influence while work discipline (Z) has a strong influence on the structural model.

Hypothesis test

To see the significant size of the hypothesis, the T test can be used, by looking at the comparison of the statistical T value with the critical T in the T test table. In the T test, there are several things you need to know, such as the following. Next, the bootstrapping output from SmartPLS is adjusted to the critical T that has been determined, namely 1.668. A hypothesis is accepted if the statistical T value exceeds the critical T value, and rejected if the statistical T value is below the critical T value. The results of hypothesis testing using bootstrapping can be seen in Table 10

Table 10. Hypothesis testing

	Hypothesis	T Statistics	T Critical (0,1)	Information
H1	X1 > Z	1,767	1,668	Hypothesis Accepted
H2	X2 > Z	1,749	1,668	Hypothesis Accepted
H3	X1 > Y	0,419	1,668	Hypothesis Rejected
H4	X2 > Y	0,472	1,668	Hypothesis Rejected
H5	Z > Y	1,823	1,668	Hypothesis Accepted
H6	X1 > Z > Y	1,420	1,668	Hypothesis Rejected
H7	X2 > Z > Y	0,996	1,668	Hypothesis Rejected

Source: Data processe

Based on Table 10, it is found that of all the hypotheses proposed in this research, 4 hypotheses were rejected. Because, based on the results of bootstrapping and the T test, this hypothesis does not exceed the predetermined critical T value. Based on the path coefficients table, it is known that the statistical T value for construct X1 against Z (H1) is greater than the critical T value (1.669), namely 1.767. This explains that the influence that X1 has on Z has proven to be significant. Then H1 can be proven. For the X2 to Z (H2) construct, it is known that the statistical T value for the X2 to Z construct is greater than the critical T value (1.669), which is 1.749. This explains that the influence that X2 has on Z has proven to be significant. Then H2 can be proven.

For construct X1 against Y (H3) it is smaller than the critical T value (1.669), which is 0.419. This explains that the influence that X1 has on Y has proven to be insignificant. So H3 cannot be proven. For construct X2 against Y (H4) it is smaller than the critical T value (1.669), which is 0.472. This explains that the influence that X2 has on Y has proven to be insignificant. So H4 cannot be proven.

For the Z construct against Y (H5) it is greater than the critical T value (1.669), which is 0.1823. This explains that the influence that Z has on Y has proven to be significant. Then H5 can be proven.

For construct Z, it can mediate construct X1 against Y (H6) which is smaller than the critical T value (1.669), which is 0.996. This explains that the influence that construct Z has on the relationship between X2 and Y has proven to be insignificant. So H6 cannot be proven. For construct Z, it can mediate construct X2 against Y (H7) which is smaller than the critical T value (1.669), which is

1.420. This explains that the influence that construct Z has on the relationship between X1 and Y has proven to be insignificant. So H7 cannot be proven.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Work Motivation on Work Discipline.

Based on the hypothesis proposed in the research, it was found that H1 was accepted. This is based on the test results, namely that the statistical T value for construct X1 against Z (H1) is greater than the critical T value (1.669), which is 1.767. This explains that the influence given by X1, namely motivation, to Z (discipline) has proven to be significant. So H1 can be proven. The accepted hypothesis is "There is an influence of work motivation on the work discipline of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service.". Motivation is a process where needs encourage a person to carry out a series of activities that lead to achieving certain goals. If needs have been met then satisfaction will be achieved. A group of unsatisfied needs will cause tension, so it is necessary to carry out a series of activities to seek the achievement of specific goals that can satisfy this group of needs, so that tension is reduced. Where carrying out a series of activities is in accordance with existing regulations at that place, namely the Tapin Regency One Stop Integrated Service and Investment Service, one of which is discipline. These two variables have equally good results with an average answer above 3. This proves that respondents assess work motivation and work discipline at the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service as good and with better employee work motivation. then the employee's work discipline also increases. The results of this research are in line with previous research by Paulus Libu Lamawitak, S. Fil, in 2014 who also found that work motivation had a significant effect on work discipline at PT. Nasmoco, Youth, Semarang.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Work Discipline

Based on the hypothesis proposed in the research, it was found that H2 was accepted. The accepted hypothesis is "There is an influence of organizational culture on the work discipline of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service.". Organizational culture refers to the system of shared meaning held by members that differentiates the organization from other organizations. This system of shared meaning, when examined more closely, constitutes a set of key characteristics valued by the organization. Where an organization has a different work culture, at the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service, working by having the courage to take risks and daring to innovate is the most approved. The desire to innovate and dare to take risks ultimately makes employees increase their discipline at work.

These two variables have equally good results with an average answer above 3. This proves that respondents assess that the organizational culture and work discipline at the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service are good and the organizational culture is getting better. If you are there, the work discipline of employees at that place will also increase. The results of this research are in line with Yusman Akram's previous research in 2017 which also found that organizational culture had a significant influence on work discipline at the Housing, Settlement and Land Service in Kotabaru Regency.

The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis proposed in the research, it was found that H3 was rejected. The hypothesis that was rejected was "There is an influence of work motivation on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency One Stop Integrated Services and Investment Service". As in the description above, you can see the statement that the salary that the respondent receives is sufficient for his and his family's needs and the statement of conditions that are specific to a job, meaning that if we want to motivate someone, we need to understand at what level that person is in the hierarchy and need to focus on focusing needs on or above that level. So that person's needs can be satisfied. In this case, the motivation to fulfill needs in terms of wages and challenges for employees is considered insufficient so that employee motivation is lacking and has an impact on the performance of these employees at the Tapin Regency One Stop Investment and Integrated Services Service.

These two variables have equally good results with an average answer above 3, but there are several items that have quite low scores, close to neutral. This means that there is still a need to improve work motivation items so that they have an impact on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service in the eyes of respondents. According to Azizatil (2021), this could happen due to the respondent's lack of understanding or perception of the questionnaire statements so that even though the results are quite good, the effect has not yet been found. The results of this research contradict previous research

by Paulus Libu Lamawitak, S. Fil, in 2014 which found that work motivation had a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Nasmoco, Youth, Semarang. According to Azizatil (2021), this result could have occurred due to differences in respondents with related research and also different research objects. Apart from that, sometimes the relationship between variables can only be significant by using a larger sample.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis proposed in the research, it was found that H4 was rejected. The hypothesis that was rejected was "There is an influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service". Organizational culture will improve employee performance by giving them a feeling of belonging, loyalty, trust, values and encouraging them to think positively about themselves and the organization. In this way, the organization maximizes employee potential and wins the competition. Organizational culture will also ultimately function as a motivator for employees in carrying out their work. If the organization is deemed unable to provide work according to the job description and its potential, in this case at the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, then this will have an impact on the performance of the organization's employees who will not be optimal in terms of their job competency.

The two variables above have equally good results with an average answer above 3, but there are several items that are close to 3 or neutral. This proves that organizational culture still needs to be improved so that it can have a significant impact on the performance of employees at the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service in the eyes of respondents. According to Azizatil (2021), this could happen due to the respondent's lack of understanding or perception of the questionnaire statements so that even though the results are quite good, the effect has not yet been found. The results of this research contradict Yusman Akram's previous research in 2017 which also found that organizational culture had a significant influence on employee performance at the Housing, Settlement and Land Service in Kotabaru Regency. According to Azizatil (2021), this result could have occurred due to differences in respondents with related research and also different research objects. Apart from that, sometimes the relationship between variables can only be significant by using a larger sample.

The Effect of Work Discipline on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis proposed in the research, it was found that H5 was accepted. The accepted hypothesis is "There is an influence of work discipline on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency One Stop Integrated Services and Investment Service". Work discipline, viewed from the science of business administration, is defined as an attitude of respect, respect, obedience and obedience to applicable regulations, both written and unwritten, as well as being able to carry them out and not evade accepting the sanctions. Good work discipline reflects a person's sense of responsibility for the tasks assigned to him. This encourages employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service to voluntarily comply with all regulations and be aware of their duties and responsibilities. So someone will obey/carry out all their duties with passion, work enthusiasm and the realization of the goals of the organization, employees and society. one of these rules is discipline.

These two variables have equally good results with an average answer above 3. This proves that respondents assess that the performance of the employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service is good and the better the employee's work discipline, the better the employee's performance. The results of this research are also in line with Yusman Akram's previous research in 2017 which also found that organizational culture had a significant influence on employee performance at the Housing, Settlement and Land Service in Kotabaru Regency.

Work discipline does not mediate the influence of work motivation and employee performance

Based on the hypothesis proposed in the research, it was found that H6 was rejected. The hypothesis that was rejected was "Work discipline has a positive effect on the relationship between motivation and performance of employees of the Tapin Regency One-Stop Integrated Services and Investment Service". Work discipline is a tool that managers use to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change behavior and as an effort to increase a person's awareness and willingness to comply with all company regulations and applicable social norms. Due to the lack of strict sanctions or warnings given to employees who violate the Tapin Regency One Stop Investment and Integrated Services Service, this can reduce employee work motivation and have an impact on the employee's own performance, as in the opinion of Pinder, (2013) who believes that work motivation is a set of a force both from within and outside a person that encourages someone to start working behavior, according to a certain format, direction, intensity

and time period. Therefore, apart from internal encouragement, external encouragement is also needed to motivate employees, in this case strict sanctions or warnings from superiors are needed to improve employee performance.

The three variables above have equally good results with an average answer above 3, however there are several items in the three variables that have a score close to 3 or neutral. This proves that there is still a need to improve work discipline regarding the relationship between work motivation and performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service in the eyes of respondents. According to Azizatil (2021), this could happen due to the respondent's lack of understanding or perception of the questionnaire statements so that even though the results are quite good, the effect has not yet been found. The results of this research contradict previous research by Paulus Libu Lamawitak, S. Fil, in 2014 which found that work discipline mediates work motivation and has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Nasmoco, Youth, Semarang. According to Azizatil (2021), this result could have occurred due to differences in respondents and research objects with related research. Apart from that, sometimes the relationship between variables can only be significant by using a larger sample.

Work discipline does not mediate the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis proposed in the research, it was found that H7 was rejected. The hypothesis that was rejected was "Work discipline has a positive effect on the relationship between organizational culture and the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service". Organizational culture is a basic pattern of thinking that is taught to new personnel as a way to feel, think and act correctly on a day-to-day basis. Therefore, strict warnings or sanctions are needed so that the agreed organizational culture can be adhered to by old members or new members who join in order to maintain organizational cultural values which are needed to improve employee performance.

The three variables above have equally good results with an average answer above 3, however there are several items in the three variables whose score is close to 3 or neutral. This proves that there is still a need to improve work discipline, organizational culture and employee performance at the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service in the eyes of respondents. According to Azizatil (2021), this could happen due to the respondent's lack of understanding or perception of the questionnaire statements so that even though the results are quite good, the effect has not yet been found. The results of this research contradict previous research by Paulus Libu Lamawitak, S. Fil, in 2014 which found that work discipline mediates organizational culture and has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Nasmoco, Youth, Semarang. According to Azizatil (2021), this result could have occurred due to differences in respondents and research objects with related research. Apart from that, sometimes the relationship between variables can only be significant by using a larger sample.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is an influence of work motivation on the work discipline of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service.
2. There is an influence of organizational culture on the work discipline of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service.
3. There is no influence of work motivation on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service.
4. There is no influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service.
5. There is an influence of work discipline on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service.
6. Work discipline does not mediate the influence of motivation on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service.
7. Work discipline does not mediate the influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service.

Recommendation

By considering the results of this research, as a contribution to science, as well as consideration for improving the performance of employees of the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, the researchers provide the following recommendations:

1. In order to improve employee discipline at the Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service, it is recommended that there is a need to increase motivation in the form of promotions for employees who excel, and it is also necessary to implement a good organizational culture.
2. In order to improve employee performance, leaders at the Tapin Regency Investment and One Stop Integrated Services Service should provide more space for their employees to innovate and provide encouragement to be more willing to take risks so as to determine clear targets for each job so that a work culture can be formed. encourage employees to be motivated to work with more discipline.
3. The Tapin Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Service should encourage its employees to come to the office on time so that they become more disciplined and make the employee's performance better.

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